

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New Pyrimidines

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4-Mercapto-6-methyl-2-(1-naphthyl)-5-acetylpyrimidine (3) has been synthesised via the condensation of 1-naphthoyl isothiocyanate (1) with enamminone (2). The syntheses of isothiazolopyrimidine, pyrazolopyrimidine and 4-substituted-pyrimidines are also described.

MANY pyrimidine derivatives exhibit interesting biological as well as medicinal applications^{1,2}. This together with our interest in the synthetic potential of fused pyrimidine systems, prompted us to investigate the synthesis of some new pyrimidine derivatives of potential biological activity.

A mixture of equimolecular amounts of α,β -unsaturated-aminoketone (enaminone) (2) and 1-naphthoyl isothiocyanate (1)³ when refluxed in dioxan gave 4-mercapto-6-methyl-2-(1-naphthyl)-5-acetylpyrimidine (3). 3 when reacted with sodium hypochlorite in a mixture of sodium hydroxide and ammonium hydroxide⁴ gave isothiazolo[5,4-*d*]pyrimidine (4a). During this conversion the sulphenamide (5b) was formed probably by the intermediary of sulphenyl chloride (5a)⁵ followed by dehydration of 5b. Alkylation of 3 with methyl iodide gave the 4-methylmercapto derivative (5c). Pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine (4b) was obtained on heating 5c with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol.

4-Hydroxypyrimidine (5d) was obtained by oxidising 3 with hydrogen peroxide in sodium hydroxide^{6,7}. The reaction of 3 with hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid gave 6-methyl-2-(1-naphthyl)-5-acetylpyrimidine (5e). Oxidation of 3 with bromine in acetic acid gave the disulphide (6) (Table 1).

Compounds 3, 4a, b, 5c-e and 6 were tested *in vitro* for biological activity against *Salmonella spp.*, *Proteus spp.*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus albus*^{6,7}. The activity was compared with that of penicillin G procaine at a concentration of 0.2 g dm⁻³. The most potent compounds were found to be 5c-d against *S. spp.*; 3, 4a against *P. spp.*; 6 against *S. albus* and 5e, 4b against *B. subtilis*.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p °C	Yield %	Mol. formula/ (Mol. wt)
3 ^a	215-17	30	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S (291.36)
4a ^b	168-70	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ S (291.36)
4b ^c	220-22	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ (274.31)
5c	95-97	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S (308.38)
5d ^e	230	30	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ (278.13)
5e ^d	149-50	25	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₂ (262.13)
6	152-53	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂ (586.25)

^aNmr δ (DMSO) 2.8 (6H, s, 2xCH₃), 7.6-7.8, 8.6-8.9 (7H, m, naphthyl); ^bNmr δ (acetone D) 2.9 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.6-7.7, 8.6-8.8 (7H, m, naphthyl); ^cNmr δ 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.6-7.7, 8.6-8.8 (7H, m, naphthyl); ^d $\nu_{\max}$ 1640 (CO), 3450 cm⁻¹ (OH).

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Unicam sp. 2 QOG spectrophoto-

meter and ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian A 60 (EM 360 L) spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out at the Microanalytical Unit, Cairo University. Preliminary antimicrobial activity experiment was carried out at Zagazig University⁸.

4-Mercapto-6-methyl-2-naphthyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (3): A mixture of 1-naphthoylthiocyanate (1; 0.01 mol) (prepared by refluxing a mixture of 0.01 mol 1-naphthoyl chloride and 0.7 g amm. thiocyanate in 20 ml dioxan for 20 min) and enaminone (2; 0.01 mol) in dioxan (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After cooling the resulting yellow solid was crystallised from methanol to yield 3.

4,5-Dimethyl-2-naphthylisothiazolo[5,4-d]pyrimidine (4a): An aqueous solution of sodium hypochlorite (20 ml; 5%) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of 3 (0.01 mol) in concentrated ammonium hydroxide (9 ml) and sodium hydroxide (9 ml; 3%). The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield pale yellow crystals of 4a.

4-Methylmercapto-6-methyl-2-naphthyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (5c): A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and methyl iodide (0.01 mol) in aqueous Na_2CO_3 (1 mol, 10 ml) was refluxed for 10 min. After cooling, the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol to yield crystals of 5c.

4,5-Dimethyl-2-naphthylpyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine (4b): A mixture of 5c (0.01 mol) and hydrazine (0.015 mol) in methanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After cooling, the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol to yield pale yellow crystals of 4b.

4-Hydroxy-6-methyl-2-naphthyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (5d): A mixture of 3 (10 mmol), hydrogen peroxide (20 ml; 30%) and sodium hydroxide (10 ml; 5%) was shaken for 5 min and then gently boiled for 3 min. After cooling in ice-water and scratching, the resulting solid was recrystallised from acetic acid to yield colourless crystals of 5d.

6-Methyl-2-naphthyl-5-acetylpyrimidine (5e): A mixture of 3 (10 mmol), hydrogen peroxide (20 ml; 30%) and acetic acid (10 ml) was shaken for 5 min and then gently boiled for 5 min. After cooling, the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol to yield colourless crystals of 5e.

Bis-[6-methyl-2-naphthyl-5-acetylpyrimidine-(4)]-disulphide (6): A solution of 3 (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was mixed with a solution of bromine (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) for 30 min. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid to yield yellow crystals of 6.

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